

Conference Abstract

Umbra krameri populations of the eastern edge of its areal: occurrence, state and eukaryotic symbionts

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Abstract

The European mudminnow, *Umbra krameri*, was a widespread fish in the lower reaches of the Dniester and Danube rivers in the first half of the 20th century. In the Dniester River, it was recorded from the junction of the Dniester and its Turunciuc branch to the estuary. Usually, now this endemic fish is found together with the weather loach *Misgurnus fossilis* and gibel carp *Carassius gibelio*. The factors that reduced its population were the construction of the Dubasari hydropower plant upstream in the 1950s and the embankment of the Lower Dniester wetlands to develop irrigated agriculture in the lower reaches of the river. After 1980, the hydrological regime of the Dniester in the spring was influenced by the Dniester hydropower complex in Ukraine, whose regime shapes the hydrology of the lower reaches of the river. Due to this, over the past 25 years, only small populations of this species have remained, recorded in the ditches of the Turunciuc branch near the Cuciurgan lake in the area of the village of Nezavertailovca, and water bodies connected to the Dniester on the border of Moldova and Ukraine south of the village of Palanca. Today, it is not easy to find it. Attempts to populate other suitable biotopes with fry obtained as a result of reproduction in aquariums were unsuccessful. Currently, *U. krameri* is listed in the Red Data Books of the region as most endangered (Moldova) and vulnerable (Ukraine), respectively. In the parasitologically surveyed individuals, inhabiting the lowers Dniester and Danube rivers

basins, 176 species of the eukaryotic commensal/parasitic symbionts were revealed: The diversity of parasites of the Lower Dniester populations is much richer and different, compared with those of the Danube basin: although the populations from the Dniester have a rich community of parasites, some typical „Dniester species” are absent or very rare. Almost all identified species present a novelty for this fish-host and 12 of them were described as previously unknown. The parasite fauna of the examined *U. krameri* includes 18 host-specific species, one species common with *U. limi* and 12 species common with *Esox lucius*. The total prevalence of invasion of fishes was 100%. The maximum number of parasite species for one fish reached 18, and usually 4 - 8. Males were slightly more infested than females. The diversity and abundance of parasites adequately reflect the ecological state of the biotopes, their hydrobiocenosis, as well as the impact of the water hydrologic regime, i.e., the intensity of hydropower plants' water discharges. The infestation of *U. krameri* with symbionts wasn't accompanied by fish morbidity or mortality. The parasitological situation of *U. krameri* populations inhabiting the eastern edge area is unfavourable and tense. The prevalence rate of *U. krameri* parasites is alarming; it is difficult to assume that such high values of infestation did not cause severe damage and even mortalities among fish. The carriage of many pathogenic parasites by this fish, under certain circumstances, may pose a potential threat to the survival of its unique populations of the Dniester River basin.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.